

COMPOSITION OF PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES

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Abstract: In this thesis, the structure of pedagogical activity and its structural structure and foreign experience in this regard are discussed.

Key words: pedagogical activity, structural structure, discussion, scientific approach, principle of activity, educational system.

Introduction

The structure of pedagogical activity.

Professional training of the teacher for the implementation of pedagogical activities. Areas of teacher activity. Use of educational tools and methods in pedagogical activity. General theoretical methods in pedagogical activity: analysis and synthesis, complex and systematic approach, logical, descriptive, comparative-typological and component analysis, objectivity, analytical conclusion. Theoretical foundations of future pedagogical activity. Practical basics of preparation for pedagogical activity. Preparation of future teachers for pedagogical activities based on foreign experiences. Advanced foreign experiences in education. The issue of improving the education system based on advanced foreign experiences. Use of international experience in improving the quality of education. Advanced foreign experiences in teaching specialized subjects.

In order to become a true master of a profession, a person must have natural abilities, certain physical and mental reforms, thorough training, personal preparation and some personal qualities. What kind of relationships should we pay attention to when directing to a pedagogical goal. A person who chooses the profession of pedagogy must first be healthy, be able to pronounce words correctly and well, be calm and composed, and be able to control oneself in dealings with others. Also, the presence of personal qualities such as liking children, the willingness to work with them confidently, politeness, the ability to think broadly, organization, and demandingness towards oneself and others also indicate that a person is suitable for pedagogical work.

Pedagogical activity, like all other activities, consists of goals, tasks, objects, subjects and components that are distinguished by their characteristics. The purpose of pedagogical activity has its own character, is determined by society,

and is mainly aimed at the comprehensive development of the personality of the young generation. This activity consists in preparing young people for the implementation of intergenerational social relations, using the natural capabilities of a person to acquire the experiences of society. Thus, although the goal of pedagogical activity is determined in a socially standard way, but in a specific pedagogical situation, the tasks arise in a non-standard way. Therefore, it requires a creative approach from the teacher based on the specific situation and being connected to the social situation by being able to see the goal.

The activity of a teacher means managing the activities of others. In other words, the activity of a teacher is based on the activity of students. For example, in a complex, conflicting situation, the pedagogue should try not to shout, not to single out one or another person, but should give an opportunity for the students to draw the correct conclusion from the given situation (stare, remain silent). , speak sharply). Of course, such a solution does not indicate a high level of consciousness of the students, but it means that they have reached the goal of the teacher. Thus, the peculiarity of the goal of pedagogical activity is that it should remain the goal of the pedagogue and the student.

Managing other people's activities is also complicated in that the goal of education projects the future of the student. Of course, this goal is close and understandable for the teacher, because he demands: "You should know, be able to do it." But the child is only one day. He lives with his anxiety, he solves the problem of today. The future is too far for him. This contradiction can be called the basis of the tragedy of education. It is very difficult for a teacher to be able to see the future and organize it by living with the spirit of the present.

Skilled pedagogues who understand this base their work on the child's needs, that is, they create their activity program in accordance with the child's program. Thus, the specificity of the purpose of pedagogical activity should be the teacher's personal initiative in determining the social task of society, that is, the increasing purpose of society in the pedagogical position of the teacher. Creative understanding of the goals and tasks of specific activities; taking into account children's interests and changing the types and content of activities in the implementation of their goals in the educational process.

The object of pedagogical work is: "Self-awareness of the subtle aspects of the spiritual life of a person who is being formed as a person - mind, feeling, will, faith." The specific aspects of the object of pedagogical activity are as follows:

A person is not a dead material of nature, but an active being who has unique individual qualities, only his own attitude and understands the

happenings in his own way. He is a participant in the pedagogical process, distinguished by his goals, motives, behavior. Thus, the object of pedagogical activity is considered the subject of this activity at the same time, and reacts differently to various pedagogical influences, but also passes those influences through its inner world and views. The teacher communicates with a person who is constantly changing and developing. Therefore, you should not apply uniform, template-like effects to it. This is a very complicated process and requires the pedagogue to always be in creative search. At the same time as pedagogues, the child is constantly influenced by the surrounding environment, spontaneous influence, versatile tools of different directions. That's why pedagogical work involves correcting (changing, correcting, renewing) all effects, even directing the student's behavior and activities in a purposeful way, that is, organizing education, self-education, and re-education. is required to stand.

In general, modern pedagogy, cooperative pedagogy is aimed at the democratization of relations in educational institutions, turning the child into a participant and assistant in the pedagogical process, and should be aimed at activating his activity. Subject: - Influencers on the student - pedagogue, parents, community. The main tool influencing the student is the personality of the teacher, his knowledge and experience. If the students do not accept the personality of the teacher, look critically at his knowledge and behavior, then his influence will not give good results. If a pedagogue can have a positive influence on a person morally, he can be a real educator, which can only be achieved if he constantly improves himself morally.

The main means of education are various types of activities in which the student participates: work, treatment, play, study. In this matter, some pedagogues understand that production work in the form of team activity as a subject is a teaching process that organizes children's lives, while others believe that it is necessary to strengthen the team through team creative work. One of the most important issues in the activity of a student and teacher is to turn the object of the student, the student, into an active participant in the realization of the goal of education, that is, into a subject that creates a system of interaction. This process can be implemented mainly by socializing the future life of a person, being able to connect his personal needs with the needs of society, and realizing its essence.

A real teacher should be able to understand and manage the main components of pedagogical activity (goal, tool, object, subject), determine the

goals, and choose the necessary means of activating the subject. But how? At the expense of what unique personal abilities, internal capabilities? What does he do based on his personality? Here we try to understand pedagogical skill from the point of view of personal activity and approach it from the point of view of the concept of a set of complex personal characteristics that ensure the organization of professional activity at a high level. Such important features include the humanitarian direction of activity, professional knowledge, pedagogical skills and pedagogical techniques. The most important for us in this tariff are the following.

First of all: pedagogical skill is a self-organizing system in the structure of the personality, and in this case, the system-building factor is the direction of humanism. Because his activity is aimed at setting up the pedagogical process at the level of the social order.

Secondly: it is the basis of the pedagogue's professional skills, and his deep, understanding and understanding pedagogical knowledge is important. Focused professional knowledge forms the basis of high professional activity that is self-organizing as a whole.

Thirdly: pedagogical ability is a factor that ensures faster improvement of pedagogical skills.

Fourthly: the technique, based on knowledge and ability, helps to firmly connect all means with the goal, thereby expanding the structure of pedagogical activity.

Thus, in the system of pedagogical skill, all the above elements are interconnected, not only its growth with the help of external influence, but also the basis for self-development. An important condition for success is the pedagogical technique that provides a tool that gives integrity: directionality and the result.

Humanistic orientation of the teacher's personality, the entire activity of the educator consists of pedagogical dramas (conflict of different opinions, struggle to prove the correctness of one's point of view). The higher the skill, the more obvious the contradictions become, as the new system proposed by the creative teacher is resisted by the new caretakers. What constitutes a person's orientation? High purpose, interests, valuable thoughts.

Determining this issue is the essence of the topic. The pedagogical orientation of each teacher is multifaceted. The following are especially noticeable in its valuable direction:

1. Self-confidence, that is, "in my example, let them see a knowledgeable, demanding, real teacher."
2. Having pedagogical tools.
3. Relying on students, children's team.
4. Pedagogical activity should be directed to the goal of humanistic strategy, creatively changing the means to the object of activity.

If a teacher is able to connect love to his work and students, he is a truly accomplished teacher. Pedagogical skill can be formed only when feeling responsible for the future, conscious aspiration and great love for children are organically connected. The high task of the teacher's activity is humanitarian orientation, which helps to define its specific goals. A first-year student takes children to an art museum and has trouble speaking there. The master teacher sees a lot during the excursion. Self-awareness, understanding of art, love for this profession, the ability to distinguish between good and bad, respect for the people of this profession, respect for nature, and most importantly, it helps to take the student to a higher level.

The humanitarian orientation of the teacher is also visible in his position as a vital asset. An example: the 9th grade students had to go to work in the garden tomorrow. But the children do not want to go to work and pick grapes. Because the grapes picked yesterday and the day before were rotting in the sun without being taken away. But the teacher insisted, "Your job is to pick grapes, the rest is not your job." Of course, the teacher knew that the children were speaking correctly, but did not support their opinion. Instead, he should have publicly said that this is happening because of his indifference and neglect, and he should have raised the issue with the appropriate leaders, and he should have thought with the students about how to save the crop. In the direction of a skilled teacher, there are two aspirations - a constant interest in the subject he is teaching and a constant need to connect with students. The fundamental basis of pedagogical skill is professional knowledge. The teacher's knowledge should be focused, on the one hand, on the subject, the subject he is teaching, and on the other hand, on the student who learns this subject.

The content of professional knowledge, the subject he teaches, his methodology, pedagogy and psychology. An important characteristic of professional pedagogical knowledge is to generalize and combine the subjects studied, that is, to ensure its complexity. Such a generalization means the selection of tools based on the basis of unification - solving pedagogical issues, analyzing pedagogical situations, and understanding the laws of personality

formation. Solving each pedagogical problem increases the essence of the entire knowledge system of the teacher, shows its importance. The comprehensiveness of professional knowledge of a skilled teacher is important in terms of generalization as well as personal views.

For example: a literature lesson in the 8th grade. A lot of literary critics: O. Sharofutdinov, U. Normatov, B. Kasimov have expressed their opinions about A. Kadiri's novel "Otgan kunlar". Readers also expressed their opinions about this novel. But if the teacher himself does not once express his point of view about this novel in the form of "In my opinion, I think", if he does not tell his inner relations, then he will never ask the student for a serious, heartfelt cannot demand their opinions. Knowledge of the theoretical foundations of sciences, the entire level of knowledge in the field of culture, the teacher's personal views and points of view should come to the fore.

Teacher skills. He is not the one who conveys what is in the book to the audience, the class, but he should be able to absorb the acquired knowledge in his way of looking at the world from his own point of view.

On the basis of pedagogical professional knowledge, the main principles and rules of his behavior and attitudes, that is, pedagogical consciousness, are formed. Each pedagogue creates these principles and rules based on his own experience, but understanding them and being able to see their laws requires constant research and study. This is done by acquiring scientific knowledge. The difficulty in teaching the teacher is the complexity of acquiring professional competence, which is that professional knowledge is formed at several levels at once in the field:

a) in the field of methodology (knowing the laws of philosophy, realizing the need to define the goal of education);

b) theoretical (knowledge of the laws of pedagogy, psychology, principle rules and forms of activity) in the field of knowledge;

d) in mastering methodical (modeling the educational process, mastering the level of construction) knowledge;

e) is formed in the field of technology (mastering the level of solving practical tasks of education and upbringing in specific conditions).

This requires an experienced pedagogue to be able to distinguish the need for sufficiently developed professional thinking, to be able to analyze and summarize the acquired knowledge in achieving pedagogical goals, and to be able to show them in a technological way. The speed of skill acquisition cannot fully ensure the growth of pedagogical knowledge. Of course, the pedagogical

practice of an excellent student at a higher educational institution is not always successful. The specific aspects of this person, which ensure successful work, also have the ability to promote professional growth.

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